

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH PERSONALIZED LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation. *The article mainly emphasizes the need to develop students' interest in learning and independent work skills, to teach using personalized educational technologies, to continuously increase the effectiveness of teaching and the quality of work. It is suggested that the main goal of the personalized lesson is to match with knowledge, thereby achieving mastery of the materials.*

Keywords: *Education, foreign language teaching, forming the personality, person-oriented lesson, personal-humanitarianism, problem-based teaching technology, creative thinking.*

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The effectiveness of the educational process and scientific research in the educational system is directly ensured by the needs of students, the level of professors and teachers, the content of the educational literature used in practice, and the infrastructure aimed at the formation of independent education of students in class and outside of class. Therefore, training professional teachers, ensuring their competitiveness in accordance with the requirements of the world labor market, training independent and creative thinking specialists is closely related to the system of the educational process in the very institutions [1].

In order for the educational materials aimed at the formation of the personality of the English language not to overload and not to bore the students, such knowledge is not provided in the school curriculum, not from areas that are completely unfamiliar to the students, but from their general education subjects. should be based on their knowledge, rather, it should be related to their practical application.

In our opinion, the ability to apply acquired knowledge in practice is a criterion for the conscious and effective assimilation of educational material aimed at the formation of personality. In order to improve the effectiveness of teaching in the educational establishments, we need to put forward several pedagogical requirements to determine and improve the content of the teaching resources in English.

Teaching a foreign language which aims at individualism should helps the student's practical activities such as independence, freedom, initiative, entrepreneurship, and creativity which are to be increased. Mastering these principles implies that the student, in addition to studying theoretical material, also performs various practical tasks. Therefore, in such a lesson, when performing various exercises, making models and mock-ups, and preparing visual materials, the student is required to work not only mentally, but also morally. This helps to increase the

student's qualifications and educational skills. Independent practical work involving personality formation strengthens the student's level of creative thinking, and developing their creative abilities is one of the main tasks of education. Creativity is the highest form of student activity and independence.

In the course of the lesson, the teacher should use methods that serve to develop the student's thinking (problem research, research, dialogue, heuristic conversation, discussion, work in groups) and create such conditions that the individual-oriented educational material the content should be interesting to the reader, suitable for their personal experience, stimulating to thinking, processed with a creative approach [2].

Individualized lessons have their own basic requirements, including the use of various technologies and methods of organizing individualized lessons, which allow to determine the knowledge, skills and competencies of the student, in this process, the whole group creating an environment to increase their activity, using different methods for the student to freely express their opinion, to perform problematic tasks, to objectively evaluate the activity according to the process of achieving the result, to give them the freedom to choose how they work, to observe the work methods of other students during the lesson analysis, not to exaggerate their shortcomings, to identify the reasons for low mastery and eliminate them in a way that does not harm the student's personality, to gain confidence in their own strength and talent [3].

Introduction of personal-humanitarian, cooperation, design, differentiated and individual, modular, problematic, free, non-coercive, dialogic, reflexive and heuristic teaching, development of critical thinking, game, student support technologies into modern pedagogical technologies possible Today, we consider personal-humanistic, design, problem-based and heuristic teaching technologies to be suitable for the set goals, without discriminating against others. It is effective to use them in research, problem solving, individual activities, development of independent critical thinking, and solving personal problems.

The personal-humanitarian technology is aimed at mastering programmatic knowledge from various disciplines related to concepts that allow the student to form a worldview. Unlike other technologies, this technology assumes the whole development of a person and is based on the principle of humanization. In its implementation, it is possible to ensure the social and cognitive activity of the student, assimilation of the subject content at a high level, as follows:

organization of cooperative action of subjects of the educational process;

- involving members of each micro-group to work in a practical lesson;
- use of active forms and methods of teaching.

The implementation of personal-humanitarian technology in the education of students includes the following stages.

Personal-humanitarian technology is distinguished from other technologies by its humanistic approach and psychotherapeutic orientation. It promotes the ideas of respecting the student in all respects, loving them and confidently looking at the possibility of creativity. In this technology, the attitude to the individual is primary, and the individual approach and human views prevail over other directions.

Problem-based learning technology is one of the most popular technologies today. In this technology, in the conditions of modern education, it is necessary to train qualified specialists according to consumer demand, to form the knowledge, skills and qualifications of students, to provide training for independent learning and practical activities. That is why the teacher is trying to find ways, technologies and methods to develop a creative approach to educational activities that the student has got.

Problem teaching means creating a problem situation under the guidance of the teacher, and organizing a lesson process that allows the creative assimilation of knowledge, skills and competences and the development of mental activity as a result of the active independent activity of the student.

Design technology is the organization of education, in which the student acquires knowledge in the form of a project through the planning process and performing practical tasks. As a result of its application, knowledge in the form of a project is acquired. Designing fully expresses the technological level of the educational process, and its implementation in practice turns the teacher into a highly qualified specialist, increases the student's influence and opens new aspects of creative activity development.

Work on the organization and conduct of the lesson should mainly consist of two parts: preparation of the lesson project and its implementation. The project is based on the activities that the teacher and the student will carry out together in the future. The lesson project begins with the analysis of information content based on the requirements of the state educational standard. The analysis focuses on how the elements of information content (knowledge, skills, qualifications and competences, experience of creative activity, relationships) are given in the programs and how they are reflected in the textbook.

A person-oriented lesson is not only the creation of a positive creative environment by the teacher, but a regular reference to the subject's experience of the student as an activity of his personal life. Working with the subject's experience in the lesson implies the use of various forms of interaction, which allows the cooperation of the teacher and the student, focused on the analysis of the learning process [4].

The main goal of a person-oriented lesson is to create conditions for the manifestation of the activity of learning. These are the means to achieve it:

- use of various technologies and methods of educational activities that allow to determine the student's ability;
- creating conditions for increasing the activity of the group during the lesson;
- use of different methods for the student to freely express his opinion and perform tasks;
- evaluate the student's activity according to the process of achieving the result;
- creating conditions for them to choose how to work;
- analyze the student's work method in the lesson, choose an effective method, master it, do not put pressure on them and do not exaggerate their own shortcomings;
- to identify the causes of low utilization and eliminate them;
- help the student to succeed in the lesson.

The main idea of a personalized lesson is to reveal the content of the subject's experience of the student on the topic under consideration, to match it with knowledge, thereby achieving mastery of the materials. In the lesson, the teacher helps the student to overcome the limitations of the subject experience.

The professional status of the teacher should be such that any opinion of the student on the content of the studied topic should be treated with respect. It must be an equal dialogue (polylogue), in which each student can express their opinion without fear on the topic under discussion. The task of the teacher is to identify and generalize, separate and support assumptions that are scientifically meaningful and suitable for the lesson. The most important thing is the collaborative search and analysis of the necessary conditions for solving educational tasks, which involves assessing the student's mastery of the educational material, how they organized their work, what tools should be used. In addition, the interaction of the student with their peers and the teacher is also important.

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